

REVIEW OF J. ZACHHUBER, *THE RISE OF CHRISTIAN THEOLOGY AND THE END OF ANCIENT METAPHYSICS* (OXFORD: OXFORD UNIVERSITY PRESS, 2020)

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Zachhuber’s book comes at a time of growing interest in philosophical content in early and Byzantine Christian thought—especially that found in Patristic figures (e.g. the Cappadocian fathers up to John of Damascus, as is the book’s focus), as well as in more traditional philosophical writers and commentators (e.g. John Philoponus, Stephanus of Alexandria, Michael Psellos, and so on). Despite the broad scope that the title implies, the book focuses on the development of the Greek concepts, *ousia* and *hypostasis*, as they were established in the theological tradition of the Cappadocian fathers in the 4th–5th centuries A.D., and became developed and transformed in the Miaphysite/Tritheist controversy (5th–6th centuries) and the later Neo-Chalcedonian reception (6th–8th centuries), ending with John of Damascus.

In Part I (pp. 15–111), Z. establishes his main thesis that “Cappadocian philosophy,” in the form of Basil and Gregory of Nyssa, established the “Classical Theory” according to which the Christian Trinity was spoken of as a single substance (*ousia*) in the three consubstantial (*homoousioi*) *hypostases* of Father, Son, and Holy Spirit (pp. 5–6; 61–62). This, however, sets up an aporetic difficulty: rather than a new philosophy of individuality, as certain theologians have claimed (e.g. Vladimir Lossky, John Zizioulas, etc.), the “Classical Theory” emphasizes the unity of the divine *ousia* at the risk of minimizing the unique individuality of the notion of *hypostasis*. Z. thus sees the reception of the Cappadocians as grappling with this *aporia* in the ensuing traditions—in Part II (pp. 113–187) with the Miaphysites, esp. Severus of Antioch, John Philoponus, Damian of Alexandria, and Peter of Callinicus; and in Part III (pp. 185–310) with the Neo-Chalcedonians, esp. John the Grammarian, Leontius of Byzantium, Pamphilus the Theologian, Theodor of Raïthu, Leontius of Jerusalem, Maximus the Confessor, and John of Damascus.

In Part II, one of the general themes Z. establishes with most Miaphysite figures is the emphasis on the “concrete” connection between the universal and particular: hence the desire to affirm the individuality of the *hypostases* with their tie to *ousia*, or specifically nature (*phusis*), by identifying the individual *hypostasis* with *phusis*—in the case of Christology, to emphasize the new “nature” formed in the Incarnation from human and divine *phusis*. This led Tritheists as, especially, John Philoponus to carry the logic further by affirming three *natures*, or *ousiai*, in the Trinity. By contrast, anti-Tritheist Miaphysites like Damian and Peter attempted to mitigate against

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Philoponus' solution by deemphasizing the concrete "link" between nature and *hypostasis*, either emphasizing the unity of the divine *ousia* in itself, apart from the *hypostases* (in Damian, p. 179) or emphasizing the *hypostases* as "parts" of the divine *ousia* (in Peter, p. 181). In Part III, Z. surveys the varying responses to the Miaphysites with the common adherence to the Council of Chalcedon's definition of the Incarnation as human and divine natures (*phuseis*) united in the one *hypostasis* of Christ/the *Logos*: hence a general desire to emphasize the distinct ontological status of *hypostasis* apart from *ousia*. Amidst the varying, distinct solutions we find in the different figures, perhaps the two highlights are Leontius of Byzantium, with his notion of *hypostasis* as pure existence distinct from *ousia* (pp. 209–211), and John of Damascus, with *hypostasis* as indicating a "historical" origin and continuity, and thus independent existence (pp. 299–300)—hence e.g. the *Logos*' *hypostasis* pre-exists in its divine, uncreated *ousia* rather than in its created, human *ousia*.

Overall, Z.'s project rightly identifies the central importance of the *ousia*–*hypostasis* division and definition to post-Cappadocian Christian thought, with particular reference to the Christological controversies of the 5th–7th centuries. In this, the work serves as a helpful and timely overview of a topic that was in dire need of collation into a single volume. Z.'s main line of argument—that the Cappadocian "classical theory" of natures and its applicability to later Christological debates—does often convince, especially in the later chapters. Considering the ambitiousness of the project, however, the book often makes rather puzzling generalisations, particularly in its first chapter.

One problem in the latter (and overall) is Z.'s claim of a unified philosophical "school" beginning with the Cappadocian fathers. In one's association of philosophical schools—e.g. Platonists, Stoics, Aristotelians, etc.—these schools would have discussed both metaphysics and epistemology/logic, ethics, the soul and psychology, and so on. By contrast in Z.'s account of the Cappadocian "school," we only find a discussion of metaphysics—and, at that, mainly universals and particulars in the context of *hypostasis* and *ousia*. In this regard it would have been better if the school of thought governing the Cappadocians and their influence, in this specific regard, were better defined as centered solely around the notion of universals and particulars, and hence more carefully discussed at the outset. (Compare e.g. George Karamanolis in *The Philosophy of Early Christianity* (London: Routledge, 2013), with both his broad discussion of these other philosophical themes and his methodological justification for what he calls "philosophy" in early Christians in pp. 1–28.) In contrast, Z's main sources for this claim are A.D. Nock and Pierre Hadot: both indispensable writers on the topic but who make the primary argument that ancient philosophies were foremostly ways of living - this seems a contrast to Z's own definition of Christian philosophy as a framework of universals and particulars.

One of the unfortunate consequences from this is that Z. rarely engages with pagan philosophical sources or influences, such as Platonists and Aristotelians, and the few times that he does, only in passing. Perhaps the reticence behind this is to emphasize the unique philosophical developments that the Cappadocians and their receivers carried forward, not just as repeating the

same philosophical claims and notions from other traditions (pp. 2–4). Indeed, Z.’s study does seem to justify this, however the reader would have been greatly helped had Z. made more effort to place the Cappadocians and their later developments within surrounding philosophical developments: for instance, the notion of *hypostasis* and *huparxis* in Plotinus, Proclus, and so on (see e.g. the excellent collection of papers in F. Romano and D.P. Taormina, eds., *Hyparxis e Hypostasis nel Neoplatonismo* (Firenze: Olschki, 1994)).

Despite the claim that previous philosophical traditions were not concerned about the individual (e.g. p. 70), it is unfortunate that Z. fails to look at Proclus and his concept of the henads: like the Neoplatonic One, they are equally “one” in their existence and transcend the intelligible categories of Being, including the distinction between universals/particulars, yet in this capacity as first principles alongside the One (and hence as gods) they are individuals paradigmatic of all individuality (see e.g. Edward Butler, “Polytheism and Individuality in the Henadic Manifold,” *Dionysius*, no. 23 (2005): 83–104). One thus needs to account for this background as a concurrent development of this period, even if no detectable influence can be found in later receivers of the Cappadocians (although see e.g. Timothy Riggs, “How to Speak of the Trinity: Henadology, Dionysius and Modern Commentary,” *Quaestiones Disputatae*, no. 2 (1/2) (2011): 70–82, who claims Proclus’ henads influence Ps.-Dionysius’ understanding of the Trinity: contrast to Z.’s claims about the emphasis of pure unity in Ps.-D., e.g. p. 255).

Z.’s treatment of sources is often strong, but some issues persist. He makes much use of several early works of Basil: the Apollinarian correspondence, *Letter 9* and *Against Eunomius*, and rightly so: these works demonstrate Basil’s early thought on the relationship between Father and Son, and express real conflict in how to best describe this, whether as “consubstantial (*homoousios*)” or “invariably alike (*homotios aparallaktos*).” However, Z provides dates for these works as if they were the scholarly consensus, where in fact the exact date of these works has been hotly debated for some decades, and our very understanding of how Basil developed as a theologian shifts depending on which documents came first! Z appears to follow Hildebrand’s *The Trinitarian Theology of Basil of Caesarea* (Washington D.C.: CUA Press, 2009), pp. 210–222, and Courtonne’s contribution to *Les Belles Lettres*, but arguments to the contrary are not presented or acknowledged. When Basil is compared to Apollinaris, a discussion of *Against the Sabellians*, traditionally ascribed to Athanasius, and now thought Apollinarian, would have been helpful, as in Basil’s own anti-Sabellian homily he shows clear knowledge of the text.

Similar problems are identifiable in the early chapters of the work. At times, the political landscape of the late 350s to early 360s is somewhat oversimplified: The *homoiousians* are treated as something of a monolith where they were in fact quite a diverse group, and given the importance of the 359/60 Synod at Constantinople, it is surprising that no mention of Eudoxius of Germanicia—overseer of the Synod and patron of Eunomius and Aetius—is made. Similarly, Cyril of Alexandria’s debt to the Cappadocians is explored at length, but the Tome of Leo is mentioned only once in the book, and Nestorius’ *Bazaar of Heracleides* in addition to his earlier works would

have been a welcome addition. As it stands, Chapters 2 and 3 give too narrow a representation of Chalcedonian debates. As a broader methodological issue, important conclusions are often drawn from very small quotations of a sentence or two, and backed up with references to the author's earlier work: longer pericopes and wider engagement with the secondary literature would be preferable, as Z's claims are valuable and would do well to be placed in the existing literature more thoroughly.

Early on, Z makes the—very important—point that the “Classical Theory” as he describes it is primarily the work of Gregory of Nyssa (e.g. p. 16), making use of what Basil had outlined and with the agreement of Nazianzen. However, after recognising this problem, Z goes on to treat Nyssa's thought as the natural completion of Basil's mission. Since Basil so frequently avoided the use of controversial terms—*homoousios* being chief amongst them—Z's position is rather tenuous indeed. However, since treating the Cappadocians as a monolith was the common practice for later theologians, this serves more as an issue of historical weakness than as a detriment to his later arguments. That Z's argument is less applicable to the 5th century than the 8th perhaps demonstrates this core issue: the closer one gets to the time of the Cappadocian fathers and the less mythologised their doctrinal unity is as a result, the weaker the claim of a “Classical Theory” becomes. It is indubitable that Gregory of Nyssa, following Basil, utterly revolutionised the way Christian theologians employed the language of natures and ordered a conceptual framework that became key to later Christian metaphysicians. Still, it often feels that this work overstates the immediacy with which this framework took hold.

In general, Z.'s work is to be commended for providing a much-needed overview on *hypostasis* and *ousia* as developed in sharply varying directions within the theological tradition—from the Cappadocians into the Miaphysites and Neo-Chalcedonians. However Z.'s methodology throughout the work needs qualification: indeed, one does not see so much the “end of ancient metaphysics” as its eclectic transformation within a rich theological context, and that mainly in the context of universals and particulars.